

Anti-Social and Anti-Art: Scoping Review

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Background: Opportunity exists to do a scoping review on comparing anti-social and anti-art, because the prefix anti is a fact of yield. The search anti-social and anti-art produced null results in PubMed.

Methods: Scoping review by one reviewer by reading three books: 'Handboek Psychopathie en de Antisociale Persoonlijkheidsstoornis' by Canton et al.¹, 'Dada: Art and Anti-Art' by Richter², and 'Art, No-Art and Anti-Art' by Ruhé³.

Results: The two tendencies in anti-art, namely non-representational art and satirical surrealism, resembled the two factors in the PCL-R. Anti-art originated in a refuge from World War One. Anti-art was the point where yes and no meet. There were suggestions that the prevalence of anti-social personality disorder (ASP) was very low in Asia. Maybe ASP was low because of the Asian culture yes equals no.

Conclusions: The result had comparison between anti-art and psychopathy and between anti-art and ASP. Future research could be on if anti-social could be the denominator of both psychopathy, i.e. no emotional empathy, and autism, i.e. no cognitive empathy. Subsequently, PCL-R's facet four would need a new denominator. Furthermore, it could be on dividing autism by the same factors of the PCL-R while changing its facets.

References

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2. Richter H. (1997). Dada: Art and Anti-Art. Thames and Hudson.
3. Ruhé H. (2019). Art, No-Art and Anti-Art. Galerie A.